

Research papers

Impact of borehole path deviations on the efficiency of a medium-deep geothermal storage system: Case study of the SKEWS MD-BTES Demosite

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ABSTRACT

Underground heat storage applications such as Medium Deep Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (MD-BTES) systems are a promising approach for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. In MD-BTES, approx. 20 to 40 Borehole Heat Exchangers (BHE) are strategically arranged at 5-m intervals, reaching depths of 400–1000 m. The first MD-BTES was constructed on the Lichtwiese campus of the Technical University of Darmstadt in 2022 to validate its technological feasibility and evaluate its economic and environmental impacts through scientific test cycles. A major challenge during construction was maintaining borehole verticality without the use of expensive directional drilling technology, to prevent borehole collisions and efficiency losses. However, gyroscopic measurements post-drilling indicated average deviations from verticality ranging between 3° and 5°.

Numerical simulations using Feflow 8.0 with favourable and unfavourable scenarios and different storage configurations demonstrated that borehole path deviations significantly affect outlet temperatures during heat discharge, the amount of heat stored and extracted, and overall storage efficiency. After 30 years of operation with inlet temperatures of 90 °C/30 °C (charging/discharging), deviations of 0–12° in the unfavourable scenario could result in 3–10 °C lower outlet temperatures during discharge and efficiency losses of 5–38 %. Conversely, in the favourable scenario, borehole path deviations had no significant impact on storage performance if all BHEs deviated in the same direction. These results enable the estimation of potential performance losses based on borehole path deviations, facilitating an economic comparison between the expected performance losses and the costs of employing directional drilling technology.

This study underscores the importance of developing cost-effective vertical drilling techniques for MD-BTES construction, which can play an important role in meeting climate protection targets.

1. Introduction

To achieve the EU climate targets [1], it is fundamental to decarbonize the heating sector [2]. Thermal energy storage plays a vital role in this transition, as renewable energy sources are subject to significant fluctuations in availability [3,4]. In particular, the seasonal storage of heat, for example from large-scale solar thermal collector fields, can provide large amounts of renewable thermal energy to buildings. However, the options are limited, for such a direct heat storage application without conversion processes [5,6]. Moreover, seasonal heat storage requires very large storage volumes [7]. Underground thermal

energy storage can be an attractive option [8–10]. This can be achieved either by using groundwater wells to store hot water directly in the subsurface in a so-called Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage system (ATES) or indirectly through conductive heat transfer by circulating the water in Borehole Heat Exchangers (BHE) as part of a Borehole Thermal Energy Storage system (BTES) [11,12]. Shallow BTES generally reach depths of approx. 30–250 m, with typically 20 to 500 BHE [13,14]. Due to the significant surface space requirement, thermal impact on shallow aquifers [15], reduced storage efficiency due to higher convective heat losses in the presence of groundwater flow, as well as lower storage capacity and flow temperatures, the concept of Medium-Deep Borehole

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Thermal Energy Storage (MD-BTES) was proposed [6,16–19]. This system is characterized by less BHE with a larger depth of approx. 400–1000 m [20,21]. By obtaining a larger storage volume with higher subsurface temperatures, fewer boreholes are required to store the same amount of energy, making MD-BTES particularly suitable for urban applications. In contrast to shallow BTES systems, the BHE in MD-BTES systems should be insulated with thermally low-conductive grout in the upper casing section and equipped with an insulated production tubing to minimize external thermal losses and internal thermal short circuits [22]. BTES are particularly effective in the crystalline basement, which is often characterized by higher thermal conductivities and low hydraulic conductivities compared to sedimentary rocks [23]. Increasing subsurface temperatures at greater depths also improve heat storage efficiency [24,25].

1.1. Case study SKEWS MD-BTES

With the aim of demonstrating the applicability of such systems, a demonstrator for MD-BTES was built at the TU Darmstadt (Campus Lichtwiese). Execution took place from August 2022 to November 2023 funded by the SKEWS project (Seasonal crystalline borehole thermal energy storage, No. 03EE4030A) [26] (Fig. 1). The geometry of the BHE was based on optimized design results, which proposed a 5 m spacing as optimal for MD-BTES under the expected thermo-physical properties [21]. The SKEWS aim has been to build a demonstration system with four coaxial 750 m deep BHE (BHE 1–4) with an axial spacing of 5 m in a triangular-centered layout. Additionally, three groundwater monitoring wells GWM 1–3 were positioned triangular around the storage to monitor chemical or thermal parameters in the groundwater. Due to cost increases during drilling caused by material supply disruptions as a result of the war in Ukraine and unexpected geological and hydro-geological conditions, a central fourth borehole (BHE 1) could not be completed [26]. After finishing the SKEWS research, an enlargement of the BTES to 19 or 37 BHE is planned for a complete commercial integration into the local district heating network of Campus Lichtwiese.

Based on geological outcrop studies [6,27,28] and drilling data [29] published prior the drilling operation, the study area was assumed to consist of massive granodiorites of the Bergsträßer Odenwald. These crystalline rocks, however, can be strongly weathered near the surface to a depth of up to 40 m. For this reason, a surface casing was installed up

to a depth of 40 m to secure the borehole against collapse in the weathered section. Fig. 2 shows the design of the coaxial BHE at the SKEWS site with the inner composite pipe made of Polypropylene (PPR) and steel [30] and the different thermally conductive cement types in the geology encountered. Three different cement types were used to enable different thermal and less hydraulic conductivities.

Maintaining the verticality of the boreholes was crucial to avoid collisions and maintain optimal BHE spacing for storage efficiency reasons [21]. In the absence of directional drilling technology, which would involve a significant increase in costs, the probability of deviation along the borehole path increases considerably with increasing depth. This risk depends on rock and rock formation properties, drilling technology, and drilling parameters [31,32].

To reduce borehole path deviation in the construction of the SKEWS system, air and water hammer technology was tested. The low rotation speed of the drill head and predominantly percussive advance, using the weight of the drill string, was expected to enable almost vertical drilling. Additionally, faster drilling speeds were anticipated to significantly reduce the overall drilling time resulting in ecological and economic benefits. However, during the drilling phase, heavily fractured and unstable bedrock was encountered, necessitating a switch to rotary drilling with bentonite-based drilling fluid for stabilization [26]. Water hammer technology could be tested in short sections. With the rotary technique, where advance is generated with a rapidly rotating tricone bit and corresponding pressure, higher borehole path deviations were expected. Further, analyses of the obtained cuttings and geophysical borehole logs revealed the presence of heavily altered basalt layers up to a depth of 160 m. These layers are underlain by granites up to about 460 m depth, which are further underlain by granodiorites (Fig. 2). Additionally, the existence of a fault zone was suggested [33].

The boreholes were measured spatially using a gyroscopic logging tool. The measurements revealed an average deviation from the vertical of 5.0° for BHE 2, 2.3° for BHE 3, and 3.3° for BHE 4 [26]. The general direction is NW to NNW (Fig. 3). The distance between boreholes increased from 8.7 m at the wellhead to 21–48 m at 750 m depth. As a result, despite a similar NW to NNW borehole trajectory, the optimal borehole spacing could not be maintained, indicating potential efficiency losses of the storage system [21].

Fig. 1. Location of the SKEWS drilling site at the Campus Lichtwiese at TU Darmstadt. BHE 2–4 have a depth of 750 m and BHE 1 was stopped in 40 m.

Fig. 2. Design of the coaxial BHE at the SKEWS site with D = Diameter, L = Length, OD = Outer Diameter, ID = Inner Diameter, SC = Surface casing. The inner blue pipe is a composite pipe of PPR and steel [30]. Only the width is true to scale. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. 3D and 2D views of the borehole paths at the SKEWS site (local coordinate system). Due to deviations the distance between the drillings increased from 8.7 m at the top to 21 m - 48 m at the bottom.

1.2. Objective of the study

In recent years, significant progress has been made in modeling Medium to Deep BTES systems, particularly in terms of reservoir properties, system design, and operational optimization. Various comprehensive parameter studies and sensitivity analyses have investigated the influence of reservoir rock properties, fluid inlet temperatures and well field layout on storage efficiency [21,24,25]. In further studies, the influence of surface network consumers and energy producers on the BTES system was examined in co-simulation studies [34,35]. Comprehensive overviews of developments in BTES research and project development can be found in the review studies by Alimonti et al. [36], Budiono et al. [37] and Kolo et al. [38].

While the modeling of vertical MD-BTES systems has been extensively studied, the influence of borehole path deviations on thermal performance remains largely unexplored. Negative effects, such as lower storage temperatures and higher temperature fluctuations, as well as diffusive heat losses, on the storage efficiency due to increased or reduced spacing in shallow storage systems, have already been documented [21,39–42]. Additionally, Steinbach et al. [43] conducted a stochastic modeling to examine the influence of deviated borehole paths on the efficiency of shallow BTES systems. In the layouts analysed, relative mean performance losses of 10 % and in extreme deviated scenarios >20 % or 30 % were observed [44]. This is limited transferable on the particular MD-BTES due to the greater depths and lower number of BHE as well as different subsurface properties.

This numerical study shows a novelty approach to investigate the impact on storage efficiency of MD-BTES using “favourable” and “unfavourable” scenarios of borehole path deviations. The results will provide a basis for approximating minimum and maximum efficiency losses for different borehole deviations and enable faster decision making in drilling campaigns. For instance, material and drilling costs of directional drilling technology can be offset against economic losses due to deviated BHE in later operation, allowing for decisions to be made during the drilling phase.

2. Methodology

Based on initial results from the research BTES in southeast Darmstadt, a study was carried out using thermo-hydraulic coupled numerical models to quantify the impact of different borehole path deviations on the efficiency of an MD-BTES system.

2.1. Theoretical background

In the numerical models in FEFLOW 8.3, groundwater flow and heat transport were simulated under fully saturated and confined conditions. Simplifying the governing equations, the groundwater in a confined porous medium can be expressed with the flow equation based on Darcy’s law [45].

$$S_s \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (K \nabla h) + Q \quad (1)$$

Here, S_s is the specific storage coefficient, h is the hydraulic head, t is the time, K is the hydraulic conductivity tensor, and Q is a volumetric source or sink term.

The governing equation for heat transport in saturated porous media is based on the classical heat conduction equation originally introduced by Fourier and later extended to porous media using volume-averaged bulk parameters,

$$(\rho c_p)_m \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_w c_{p,w} v \cdot \nabla T = \nabla \cdot (\lambda_m \nabla T) + Q_T \quad (2)$$

where $(\rho c_p)_m$ is the volumetric heat capacity of the porous medium, T is the temperature, ρ_w and $c_{p,w}$ are the density and specific heat capacity of

water, v is the Darcy velocity vector, λ_m is the thermal conductivity of the saturated medium, and Q_T is the heat source/sink term.

The quasi-stationary analytical solution by Eskilson and Claesson [46–48] is used for simulating Borehole Heat Exchangers (BHE), and is based on a comprehensive analytical framework involving g-functions. While the following expressions represent a simplified formulation that captures the essential long-term temperature response of the ground, the full model includes a variety of additional relationships. These account for thermal resistances between the circulating fluid and borehole wall, both short- and long-term heat transfer dynamics, borehole field geometries, temporal and spatial superposition principles, as well as internal temperature distributions along and across the borehole depth.

$$T(t) - T_0 = \frac{q'}{2\pi\lambda_m} G(\tau) \quad (3)$$

Here, $T(t)$ is the borehole wall temperature at time t , T_0 is the undisturbed ground temperature, q' is the linear heat exchange rate per borehole length, and $G(\tau)$ is the non-dimensional temperature response function. The dimensionless time τ is defined as

$$\tau = \frac{\alpha_m t}{H^2} \quad (4)$$

where α_m is thermal diffusivity, H is borehole depth and t is time.

The recovery efficiency η of a BTES, as already described in [21,38], is defined as the quotient of the extracted heat Q_E by the stored heat Q_S during one operation cycle.

$$\eta = \left| \frac{Q_E}{Q_S} \right| \quad (5)$$

Since BHE are closed-loop systems, heat can only be conductively transferred from the circulating fluid to the surrounding storage medium, i.e. the natural subsurface. Therefore, the heat rate ΔQ can be calculated with the temperature difference ΔT of the inlet and outlet fluid, its volumetric heat capacity $(\rho c)_f$ and its flow rate \dot{V} through the BHE array.

$$\Delta Q = \Delta T \cdot (\rho c)_f \cdot \dot{V} \quad (6)$$

For comparing the efficiency of the BHE in different storage sizes, the extracted heat Q_E from one extraction cycle must be normalized by the BHE lengths L_{tot} and the duration of one extraction period Δt . This gives the specific extraction rate \dot{q} per borehole.

$$\dot{q} = Q_E \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta t \cdot L_{tot}} \quad (7)$$

To integrate a realistic site-specific trajectory of a deviated borehole into the models, the trajectories of the three drilled boreholes BHE 2, 3, and 4 were used to create an averaged deviated borehole by calculating the mean values of the corresponding x and y coordinates at each depth (z coordinate) from the three boreholes (Fig. 4 A-D). The average deviation is about 3° with a spatial orientation of 308°. To consider different degrees of deviation, the averaged deviated borehole was mathematically adapted using a tangential function $f(z)$, as shown in [44].

$$f(z) = \frac{\tan(\text{rad}(\alpha))^* z^a}{750^{a-1}} \quad (8)$$

$$x_{\text{coordinate}} = \frac{\tan(\text{rad}(\alpha))^* z^a}{750^{a-1}} \cdot \sin(\arctan^2(0, x) + \text{rad}(\beta)) \quad (9)$$

$$y_{\text{coordinate}} = \frac{\tan(\text{rad}(\alpha))^* z^a}{750^{a-1}} \cdot \cos(\arctan^2(0, x) + \text{rad}(\beta)) \quad (10)$$

$$z_{\text{coordinate}} = z \quad (11)$$

The function $f(z)$ describes the degree of deviation with the depth z and reproduces the curve trajectory of the averaged deviated borehole

Fig. 4. Averaged borehole trajectory (in orange) from the three real trajectories of BHE 2–4 and the tangential function curve (in purple) (Vertical exaggeration: A, E, and F approx. 6×; B and C approx. 13×). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

with the “bending” factor $a = 1.6$.

By varying α , the degree of deviation of the virtual borehole trajectory from the vertical is adjusted, allowing for the generation of differently deviated virtual trajectories. By converting to polar coordinates with $\arctan^2(0, x)$, the curves can be spatially aligned in the x and y directions using the angle β (0–360°).

Considering an azimuth deviation to 308° with an average vertical deviation of 3°, the virtual trajectory represents the average deviated borehole very well (Fig. 4A–D). The Euclidean distances between the two curves are between 0 and 2 m over the entire depth, resulting in a coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.986$.

To investigate an unfavourable and favourable scenario, a ‘fan

arrangement’ and an ‘arc arrangement’, were implemented (Fig. 4E and F), which were considered to reasonably represent opposing cases. In the fan arrangement, the direction of deviation of each borehole has been chosen such that the distance between boreholes increases maximally with depth, assuming large losses of storage efficiency. In the arc arrangement, the direction and magnitude of the deviation were equal for all boreholes. In this case all borehole paths deviate from the vertical but are still parallel. Hence, the optimal distance between the boreholes of 5 m remains constant to the final depth of 750 m. For comparability, all boreholes were limited to a length of 750 m, which means that larger deviations lead to a reduced true vertical depth (TVD) (Table 1).

According to the SKEWS expansion stages, which ensure a hexagonal

Table 1
Examined borehole deviations for the arc and fan arrangement in the 7, 19 and 37 BHE storage configurations. Reduced TVD of the deviated boreholes due to the length restriction of 750 m.

BHE No.		1	2 – 7	8 – 19	20 – 37	Deviation	TVD
Deviation	Vertical****	0°	0°	0°	0°	0°	750 m
	Arc arrangement	3°	3°	3°	3°	1°	750 m
		5°	5°	5°	5°	2°	749 m
		6°	6°	6°	6°	3°	749 m
		9°	9°	9°	9°	4°	748 m
		12°	12°	12°	12°	5°	747 m
		0°	1°	2°	3°	6°	745 m
	Fan arrangement	0°	2°	4°	6°	8°	742 m
		0°	3°	6°	9°	9°	740 m
		0°	4°	8°	12°	10°	737 m
		0°	5°	10°	-	12°	732 m
		0°	6°	12°	-	-	-
		0°	-	-	-	-	-

storage core, configurations of 7 BHE, 19 BHE, and 37 BHE were investigated (Fig. 1). The borehole path deviations were varied between 1 and 12° depending on the expansion stage to define the outer efficiency limits (Table 1). Models with 37 BHE were initially created. The reduction to a storage size of 19 BHE and 7 BHE results from the removal of the outer BHE in each case. A vertical model serves as a reference. It

was calculated in a structured and unstructured grid to identify the influence of the grid design on the results.

2.2. Model design

To implement the deviated boreholes in the numerical model, it was

Fig. 5. Vertical cross-section through a fan and arc arrangement model in FEFLOW 8.0 in an unstructured grid with three different rock types (A and B). Top view of the two different methods of serial connection in a 37 BHE configuration (C and D).

necessary to create an unstructured grid, using MeshIt [49] and meshing features within FEFLOW 8.0 [50]. Ensuring a numerical stability and reliable results, the distance of the BHE nodes was set to 1 m and additionally, 6 help nodes around each BHE at a distance of 0.74 m were added, considering a specific distance factor [48]. The thermo-hydraulic coupled simulation was finally carried out in FEFLOW 8.0 using the PETSc KSP solver.

The geological model was simplified to the occurrence of three rock units: Basalt, G1 Granite, and Granodiorite (Fig. 5). Furthermore, fully saturated groundwater conditions were assumed. However, groundwater flow was excluded in order to isolate the effect of borehole path deviation. The assigned rock properties (Table 2) were based on the latest measurement data, outcrop studies [6] and corresponding databases [51].

Due to limited input options in FEFLOW 8.0, the BHE geometry (Fig. 2) had to be integrated into the model in a simplified form (Table 3). Accordingly, the thermally highly conductive cement with $3.0 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ was assumed for the entire BHE length and only the low-conductivity PPR with $0.4 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ was considered for the composite inner pipe (PPR and steel). The upper surface casing up to 40 m was also excluded.

With regard to the other model parameters, the geothermal gradient was measured to be 20 K km^{-1} by temperature logging in EWS 2–4, which we used to determine the lower temperature level of our model (Table 4). Prior to the transient simulation a steady state simulation was performed with the Dirichlet boundary condition for hydraulic head and temperature.

Half-yearly cycles of 182.5 days loading and unloading, representing a simplified seasonal charging and discharging operation of the BTES system were applied. The charging temperature of $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ results from the upper system limit for the PPR materials used within the BHE and possible charging temperatures from solar thermal collectors or CHP units. The inlet temperature of $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ during discharge was selected to allow the theoretical operation of the BTES without a heat pump in a 4th-generation district heating network [52]. All simulations were carried out with a pumping rate of 4 l s^{-1} through each of the parallelly connected BHE. This value is sufficiently high to ensure turbulent flow within the BHE and to reduce heat transfer between the inner pipe and the annular space, while still being low enough to allow for efficient pump control at low pressures and total flow rates. For models with a storage configuration of 37 BHE, two different series connections were additionally examined (Fig. 5). By connecting the BHE in series during charging, the hot water is first circulated through the central BHE before it flows through the outer BHE. Thereby, it is gradually cooled. However, with a lower overall flow rate and total amount of energy, a higher temperature level is achieved in the storage core, which gradually decreases towards the outside of the storage edge. When discharging, the water is then normally circulated from the storage edge to the inner BHE to take advantage of the gradual temperature increase to the storage core. Due to limitations in switching circulation directions in FEFLOW 8.0, the water from the inner BHE was also circulated to the storage edge

Table 2

Assigned rock properties in the FEFLOW models. Measurements from cuttings* and outcrops**. Parameters from database*** [6,51] considering drilling logs and cuttings.

Rock properties	Unit	Value		
Rock types	[–]	Basalt	G1 Granite	Granodiorite
Depth	[m]	0–160*	160–430*	430–1000*
Thermal conductivity	$[\text{W}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}]$	1.9***	2.6**	3.3*
Volumetric heat capacity	$[\text{MJ m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}]$	1.95***	2.19***	2.22***
Porosity	[–]	0.070***	0.026**	0.005**
Hydraulic conductivity	$[\text{m s}^{-1}]$	1.15e-04***	6.50e-06***	5.00e-08***

Table 3

BHE and grout settings in FEFLOW.

BHE properties	Value
Computational method	Quasi-stationary (Eskilson & Claesson) [46–48]
Geometry	Coaxial central inlet (CXC)
Borehole diameter	0.2413 m
Inlet pipe diameter	0.1143 m
Inlet pipe wall thickness	0.01965 m
Outlet pipe diameter	0.01778 m
Outlet pipe wall thickness	0.008 m
Inlet pipe thermal conductivity	$0.4 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Outlet pipe thermal conductivity	$54 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Grout volume thermal conductivity	$3.0 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Fluid thermal conductivity	$0.65 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Fluid volumetric heat capacity	$4.145 \text{ MJ m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Fluid dynamic viscosity	$0.504\text{e-}03 \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Fluid density	$0.977\text{e}+03 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$

Table 4

Properties for the FEFLOW models.

Model properties	Value
Hydraulic head and gradient	0 m
Surface temperature	$10.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Geothermal gradient	0.02 K m^{-1}
BHE spacing surface	5 m
BHE length	750 m
Model width/length	250 m – 400 m
Number of nodes	330 K – 560 K
Number of elements	2.0 M – 3.4 M
BHE inlet temp.	$90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} / 30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Inlet temp. Switching	182.5 d
Pumping rate per BHE	$4 \text{ l s}^{-1} (4.22 \text{ l s}^{-1})$
Storage configuration	Parallel: 7 BHE, 19 BHE, 37 BHE Serial: 19 → 18 BHE, 1 × 7 and 5 × 6

during discharging. In the case of the serial connection of the 19 inner BHE with the 18 outer BHE (19 → 18, Fig. 5), the flow rate for the 18-BHE ring increased to 4.22 l s^{-1} per BHE.

A total of 59 models were calculated within the study. Furthermore, some additional models with higher and lower degrees of grid refinement were computed to ensure grid independency.

3. Results

To evaluate the effects of the borehole path deviations on the BTES, the simulation results were analysed using the key evaluation parameters of fluid temperatures, stored and extracted heat and, in particular, the storage efficiency. This quantifies the heat losses and the fluid temperatures inform about the potential for integration into a district heating network. The nearly identical curve shape of the vertical structured and unstructured models ensure that the grid design and calculation of the unstructured models is accurate.

3.1. Outlet temperatures

For the integration of a BTES into a district heating network, the available temperature at the storage outlet during discharging is crucial to plan for the necessity of a heat pump and its sizing. In the conducted simulations, a $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ warm fluid was circulated into the BHE during the extraction period, and the temperature at the collective MD-BTES outlet was recorded.

As expected, all models show a decrease in outlet temperatures over the course of a given extraction cycle. Moreover, the temperatures depend on the borehole path deviation. In the storage configuration with 37 BHE (fan arrangement, parallel connection), the outlet temperatures in the 5th year of operation are between approx. $41.0\text{--}44.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at the

beginning of the extraction period and decrease to 31.8–33.8 °C at the end of the period, depending on the borehole path deviation (Fig. 6B). In the 30th year of operation, outlet temperatures range between 42.0 and 44.5 °C at the beginning and 32.2–34.1 °C at the end of the extraction period (Fig. 6C).

It is particularly notable that in the vertical model, the temperature in the first month of the extraction period is 3–10 °C higher than in the models with deviated borehole paths. However, in the course of the extraction phase, the temperature of the vertical models decreases to a greater extent.

For the smaller storage configurations with 7 BHE and 19 BHE, a similar pattern is observed. In the 5th year of operation at the beginning of the extraction temperatures, depending on the borehole path deviation, range from 40.0 to 44.0 °C (19 BHE) and 40.0–42.2 °C (7 BHE) and decrease to 31.0–33.0 °C (19 BHE) and 30.8–31.1 °C (7 BHE) at the end of the period (Fig. 6K and N). During the 30th year, outlet temperatures initially range from approx. 41.8–44.5 °C (19 BHE) and 41.0–43.0 °C (7 BHE), dropping to 32.2–34.0 °C (19 BHE) and 32.0–33.2 °C (7 BHE) by the end of the extraction period (Fig. 6L and O).

The results of the series connection are particularly interesting since significantly higher outlet temperatures can be achieved. For example, in the 5th of operation with the series 19 to 18 BHE connections, depending on the borehole path deviation, temperatures drop between 47.5 and 53.5 °C at the beginning to 32.1–36.1 °C (Fig. 6E). In the 30th year of operation, outlet temperatures are between 48.0 and 54.0 °C at the beginning and 34.5–37.5 °C at the end of the extraction period (Fig. 6F).

Through the series 1 × 7 and 5 × 6 BHE configuration, even higher outlet temperatures can be achieved, depending on the borehole path deviation. At the beginning of the extraction period in the 5th year of operation, temperatures between 50.0 and 68.1 °C are achieved, which drop to 32.2–41.9 °C at the end. In the 30th year of operation, the temperatures are 58.8–70.0 °C at the beginning and decrease to 40.2–46.1 °C by the end of the extraction period (Fig. 6I).

In case of the arc arrangement, almost identical curve progressions of outlet temperatures are observed for the different borehole path deviations, which match the vertical unstructured model (Fig. 7A–I).

Slight divergences from the curves of the vertical unstructured models occur for the 7 BHE models with borehole path deviations of 5° and 12° in the 5th and 30th year of operation. The curve is slightly wavy and lies below the other models (Fig. 7H and I).

3.2. Stored and extracted heat

In addition to the outlet temperatures, the consideration of the storage capacity, i.e. the amounts of stored and extracted energy, is also crucial for the dimensioning of a storage system.

In a storage configuration of 37 BHE (parallel operation, fan arrangement) approx. 16.8–21.9 GWh a⁻¹ can be stored and 13.5–15.5 GWh a⁻¹ can be extracted in the 30th year of operation considering borehole path deviations between 0 and 12° (Fig. 8A). This corresponds to average specific extraction rates \dot{q} of 98–180 W m⁻¹ per BHE in a system of 37 BHE with a length of 750 m. The differences in stored and extracted heat are particularly largest in the initial years. For example, after 5 years of operation, these range from 17.7 to 27.5 GWh a⁻¹ for stored heat and only 6.7–14.0 GWh a⁻¹ for extracted heat. It is apparent that there is a greater range in the amounts of stored energy for the various borehole path deviations than in the amounts of extracted heat.

A similar behavior is observed for the 37 BHE in both types of serial connection and for the storage configurations with 19 BHE and 7 BHE (Fig. 8B–E) in parallel connection. In general, the stored and extractable energy amounts as well as the specific heat rate tend to decrease compared to the 37 BHE storage configuration. In the 30th year of operation, 9.0–12.5 GWh a⁻¹ (19 BHE) and 3.7–4.8 GWh a⁻¹ (7 BHE) can be stored, while 5.0–7.2 GWh a⁻¹ (19 BHE) 1.5–2.3 GWh a⁻¹ (7 BHE) can be extracted, depending on the borehole path deviation

(Fig. 8D and E).

For the arc arrangement (Fig. 9A–E) an influence of the borehole path deviation on the heat quantities can hardly be determined.

3.3. Storage efficiencies

Using the stored and extracted heat, the efficiency of the storage system can be determined for different borehole path deviations and storage configurations. The simulation results show that for a storage expansion stage of 37 BHE with parallel connection and borehole path deviations between 0 and 12° in the fan arrangement, efficiencies after 30 years range between 55 and 85 % (Fig. 10A). Thus, larger borehole path deviations significantly reduce the storage efficiency. In addition, the efficiency increases much more slowly with higher deviations, so the difference in efficiency is particularly large in the first few years of operation (e.g. ~25 % to ~75 % after 5 years of operation).

When operating the 37 BHE storage in serial mode 19 to 18 BHE, the efficiencies drop by a few percentage points to around 22–73 % after 5 years and 52–82 % after 30 years of operation compared to parallel connection (Fig. 10B). The curves look very similar to parallel operation, only slightly shifted downwards.

In the serial operating mode 1 × 7 and 5 × 6 BHE, the efficiencies decrease further compared to the 19 to 18 BHE serial operation mode. Values range between only 10 % – 63 % after 5 years of operation and 37–75 % after 30 years of operation (Fig. 10C). With very large deviations of 10° and 12°, no storage effect can be observed in the 1st and 2nd year, which is why the efficiencies initially fluctuate here.

A size reduction to 19 BHE (parallel operation, fan arrangement) also leads to a reduction in efficiencies compared to the 37 BHE system. The 19 BHE arrangement (Fig. 10D) reaches efficiencies of about 18–65 % after 5 years and 40–75 % after 30 years of operation depending on the magnitude of deviation. Again, the models with larger borehole path deviations in particular show a diminished increase in storage efficiency in the initial years of operation and a significant reduction in efficiency overall.

With a further size reduction to 7 BHE (Fig. 10E), storage efficiencies show an even larger decrease to 15–45 % after 5 years and 32–58 % after 30 years of operation depending on the borehole path deviations that ranged from 0 to 6° in this scenarios.

For each of the BHE size and connection scenarios, simulations of the arc arrangement reveal almost identical results and curve progressions, regardless of the borehole path deviation (Fig. 11A and 10B).

To summarise, the trends in the storage efficiencies in the unfavourable scenario (fan arrangement) clearly show that the greater the borehole path deviations, the greater the loss in efficiency. In particular, a significantly longer start-up phase is required before maximum efficiencies are achieved.

4. Discussion

4.1. Influence of borehole path deviation

The results show that in the unfavourable scenario (fan arrangement), the borehole path deviation has a significant influence on the outlet temperature, the amounts of stored and extracted heat as well as the storage efficiency in all scenarios investigated. In [21], an optimum BHE distance of 5 m was determined. Larger or smaller BHE distances lead to a reduction in storage efficiency. A larger borehole spacing means that during the charging phase, the individual heat plumes around the BHE only barely meet or overlap. This results in a high radial temperature gradient from the borehole wall to the centre distance of the next BHE. This leads to a persistent conductive heat flow away from the BHE even after the charging phase. Accordingly, the outlet temperatures at the BHE drop very quickly again with greater borehole path deviation, especially at the beginning of the discharging phase.

In the vertical models with optimum BHE spacing, on the other hand,

Fig. 6. Complete simulation over 30 years and selected outlet temperatures of the total BHE outlet with different storage configurations and with varying borehole path deviations in the fan arrangement.

Fig. 7. Outlet temperatures of the total BHE outlet with different storage configurations and with varying borehole path deviations in the arc arrangement.

the heat plumes overlap, which results in higher temperatures in between two neighbouring BHE and thus significantly lower temperature gradients. Consequently, significantly higher outlet temperatures can be achieved over a longer period of time.

As the operating time increases, the temperature differences between the vertical model and those with deviated boreholes become smaller. At the end of the discharging phase, outlet temperatures in the models with deviation are sometimes even higher than those of the vertical model (Fig. 6). Systems with greater borehole path deviation open up a larger storage volume, which ultimately heats up more and more with increasing operating time. As the operating time increases, this effect also has a positive impact towards the end of the extraction phases. When the storage volume in the vertical model has already been emptied, models with drilling path deviation still draw energy from the far field.

This can be confirmed by analysing the stored and extracted heat. The stored heat increases significantly with larger borehole deviations, whereas the amount of extractable heat decreases with increasing borehole path deviation (Fig. 8). The different temperature development also causes the differences in the stored and released heat quantities. With increasing borehole path deviation, more heat can be stored due to the larger temperature gradient, whereas the absolute temperature in the storage increases less. During discharging with an inlet temperature of 30 °C, less heat can be extracted due to the lower temperature level in the storage. Consequently, with larger deviations, the temperature gradient during charging increases and decreases during discharging,

which has a significant influence on the performance and the amount of heat that can be transferred.

The storage efficiency is defined as the ratio of the amount of heat stored to the amount of heat extracted in an operating year. If more and more heat is stored and less and less heat is extracted as the borehole path deviation increases, this also explains why the storage efficiency decreases strongly as the borehole path deviation increases. In particular, this can be observed with larger borehole path deviations, so that significant losses in performance can be expected in the first 3–6 years of operation and the achievement of 80 % of the final efficiency occurs significantly later [21,53,54]. For example, deviations of 10° and 12° do not lead to an overlap of individual heat plumes around the BHE in the first few years due to the very large borehole spacing.

In the favourable scenario (arc arrangement), there is no significant influence on the outlet temperature, the stored and extracted heat, or the storage efficiency with different borehole path deviations. Regardless of the deviation, the borehole spacing remains the same due to the selected geometry, so that there is no increase in storage volume between the BHE. Accordingly, the effects described above do not occur. However, as the deviation increases, the true vertical depth of the BHE becomes smaller and smaller for the same BHE length. Consequently, the natural bottom hole temperatures become slightly smaller as well. With a deviation of 12°, this means a true vertical depth of only 732 m instead of 750 m and a bottom hole temperature that is 0.36 °C lower than in the vertical system. However, this negative effect was not noticeable in the simulations conducted.

Fig. 8. Stored and extracted heat and the average specific heat rate with different storage configurations and with varying borehole path deviations in the fan arrangement.

4.2. Influence of storage size and series connection of BHE

Smaller storage systems with 19 BHE or 7 BHE show similar behavior when the borehole path deviation is increased in the unfavourable and favourable scenarios. The effects described about the increase in storage volumes and the increase in the temperature gradient from the borehole wall to the centre distance of the next BHE in Chapter 8.1 can also be observed. However, the effects are stronger due to the less favourable volume to surface ratio. Diffusive heat losses at the edge of the storage are more considerable with the smaller storage volume.

Considering the lower storage efficiencies in the vertical models of approx. 75 % for 19 BHE and 58 % for 7 BHE, even small deviations lead to very inefficient storage systems.

Connecting the BHE in series increases the output temperatures of the storage systems, which is of particular interest when integrating the systems into heating grids. For example, the dimensioning of a heat pump plays a decisive role in the economic efficiency of an MD-BTES. In 4th generation heating grids, flow temperatures of approx. 50–60 °C with return temperatures of approx. 25 °C are required [55]. These temperature levels cannot be achieved with a parallel connection of BHE without a heat pump. However, with a series connection, temperatures >50 °C (19 to 18 BHE) and > 60 °C (1 × 7 and 5 × 6 BHE) can be achieved in the first half of the discharging phase, which enables direct operation without a heat pump.

The reduced amounts of heat stored and extracted for the series connected systems can be explained by the overall lower flow rates and the lower temperature gradients between the BHE fluid and the subsurface when flowing through multiple series-connected BHE. This is particularly apparent with the 1 × 7 and 5 × 6 BHE serial connection. As with the parallel connections, due to increasing borehole path

deviations, there is insufficient heat to induce a thermal interaction between the BHE. Therefore the stored heat increases, whereas the extractable heat decreases and so the overall efficiency drops. This effect is further increased in the serial connection, especially for the BHE with higher deviations at the edge, since the majority of the heat transfer has already taken place when the fluid flows through the inner BHE. As a result, the storage efficiency is reduced in serial connection compared to parallel connection, the more BHE are connected in series towards the edge of the storage. In addition, the flow direction of the fluid during the extraction phase from the hot storage core to the cooler storage edge could also cause a reduction in heat transfer in the outer boreholes. However, the 19 to 18 BHE serial connection could be an attractive option for achieving higher temperature levels, as the stored and extracted heat are only approx. 9 % and the storage efficiency only approx. 3 % below that of the parallel connection. An increasing borehole path deviation with series connection of the 37 BHE has a similarly significant negative effect as with parallel connection.

As expected, no significant differences in the outlet temperature, the stored and extracted heat and the storage efficiency are observed in the favourable scenario with increasing borehole path deviations due to the constant distances between the BHE.

4.3. Simplifications and limitations of the study

In modeling, it is essential to balance the complexity of the model against computational effort and the meaningfulness of the results. An overly complex model can also make evaluation more problematic, as it becomes difficult to accurately attribute effects to causes. In this study, the reduction of model complexity particularly involves the following parts: the geological units, hydrogeological conditions, charging and

Fig. 9. Stored and extracted heat and the average specific heat rate with different storage configurations and with varying borehole path deviations in the arc arrangement.

discharging temperatures and cycles, flow rates, and the arrangement of borehole paths are simplified and are limited to only two specific scenarios. As this study primarily aimed to highlight the influence of borehole path deviations on the efficiency of an MD-BTES, additional variability or complexity in the geological or hydrogeological conditions, as well as in the operation of the storage system, would have represented additional degrees of freedom. This would have obscured the relationship between borehole path deviation and efficiency. Furthermore, by modeling an unfavourable and a favourable scenario of borehole path deviations, a statistical approach, for example based on a monte carlo study that would have required several thousand simulations for statistical evaluation, was avoided [44,56]. The unfavourable scenario is one of the disadvantageous scenarios in which a collision of the boreholes is avoided. There are probably even more unfavourable scenarios in which, for example, the boreholes all meet in the middle and the storage volume is drastically reduced. However, as with the three drilled BHE as part of the SKEWS project, it is expected that the orientation of the boreholes will align more closely with geological structures, suggesting that in reality, boreholes are likely to follow the favourable scenarios with a similar direction, rather than an unfavourable scenario with maximal divergence of boreholes [31,57,58]. Accordingly, when constructing an MD-BTES, the initial prognoses of outlet temperatures, stored and extracted heat or storage efficiency should consider the results of the unfavourable and favourable scenarios in combination, depending on the divergence and deviation of the boreholes.

A significant effect of borehole path deviation on the efficiency of shallow BHE storage was already identified in Steinbach et al. [43]. Efficiency losses are likely even greater, as thermal insulation at the upper part of the BHE was not considered in this study. Accordingly,

with near-surface insulation, heat would predominantly be introduced into deeper areas, where due to the borehole path geometry, the distances between BHE increase with depth.

5. Conclusion and outlook

This study has highlighted the importance of verticality in borehole drilling during the construction of an MD-BTES system as borehole path deviations can cause significant temperature and efficiency losses.

In a numerical simulation study, an unfavourable and a favourable scenario of the borehole deviation were analysed comparatively. The boreholes in the unfavourable scenario were arranged in a fan pattern, maximizing the distance between them as depth increases. Conversely, in the favourable scenario, the boreholes were arranged in an arc pattern, maintaining a constant distance between them by deviating in the same direction.

The comparison of these two scenarios clearly reveals that increasing the borehole spacing due to unfavourable borehole path deviations in particular has a significant negative influence on the outlet temperature during discharge, the stored and extracted heat quantities and ultimately the efficiency of a storage system. Larger BHE spacings significantly impair the thermal interaction between the individual BHEs.

For example, a deviation of only 3° in the unfavourable scenario already causes a significant reduction in outlet temperatures by an average of approx. 3–10 °C during discharging. To compensate for this temperature drop, either significantly more heat must be injected into the subsurface to heat up the larger storage volume or the operation time must last several years longer. Similar effects are observed on the storage efficiency, so that after 30 years of operation in a 37 BHE configuration with borehole path deviations of 0° - 12°, the overall efficiencies range

Fig. 10. Efficiencies for different storage configurations and with varying borehole path deviations in the fan arrangement.

Fig. 11. Efficiencies for different storage configurations and with varying borehole path deviations in the arc arrangement.

only from 55 to 85 %. In addition, depending on the magnitude of deviation, it takes significantly longer than 5 years to reach 80 % of the final storage efficiency than for a system with vertical boreholes.

For smaller storage configurations with only 19 and 7 BHE, the negative effects of the borehole path deviation are even more distinct. Reducing the size of the storage alone has a negative impact on the outlet temperature, the amount of heat stored and extracted, and the efficiency of the storage system, which is further intensified by the additional deviations in the unfavourable scenario. Accordingly, especially with smaller storage systems, attention should be paid to

maintaining the BHE spacing.

Moreover, different series connection schemes of the 37 BHE were investigated. The results reveal that higher outlet temperatures of $>50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (series connection 19 to 18 BHE) and $>60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (series connection 1×7 and 5×6 BHE) can be achieved during discharging. However, series connection also has a negative effect on storage capacity and efficiency. Nevertheless, series connection of 19 to 18 BHE could be an attractive option. Higher temperature levels can be achieved, while the stored and extracted heat quantities are only about 9 % lower and the storage efficiency is only about 3 % lower than for models with parallel

BHE connection. However, with borehole deviations of 0–12°, outlet temperature losses of 4–10 °C and efficiencies of 52–82 % can be expected after 30 years of operation.

These performance losses are associated with economic losses, which must be weighed against the initial investment costs and the potential for more expensive directional drilling. Additionally, during the drilling phase of an MD-BTES system, it is now possible to estimate the maximum performance losses expected with the present deviations and determine whether a switch to directional drilling becomes economically necessary. However, for a more accurate estimation, detailed models are recommended, as it is expected that the boreholes will likely follow the geological structures at the site and therefore are likely to deviate in similar directions. If all boreholes deviate almost identically, almost no performance losses are expected.

Furthermore, it will be important to verify the simulation study with real data from MD-BTES and particularly consider groundwater flow and more complex geological conditions, which can lead to varying degrees of heat migration depending on the deviation of the boreholes. This will be achieved with the analysis of the SKEWS test operation, where the storage effect of the three-BHE storage system will be examined based on real data from several heating and cooling phases. The results will then be implemented in numerical models and scaled up to 19 BHE and 37 BHE, respectively.

There is also further research needed in the development of cost-effective vertical drilling systems for deeper drilling. By maintaining verticality, the efficiency losses of an MD-BTES are minimized, and its economic attractiveness is further enhanced. A final economic and ecological assessment of an MD-BTES system is planned upon completion of the SKEWS test operation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Matthias Krusemark: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lukas Seib:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Max Ohagen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Bastian Welsch:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Hung Tien Pham:** Resources, Project administration. **Ingo Sass:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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